

PECULIARITIES AND DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATING OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS

Author: Toshnazarova Gulrukh Nurnazar kizi

Supervisor: Bolibekova Mavjuda Mardievna

Abstract. In this article we used the method of scientific observation, discourse analysis and content analysis of translations of English-Uzbek [or English Russian] documentation in order to verify, systematize the features of translation of official business documentation in our work.

Key words: Discourse, false friends, official translation, diplomatic documents, linguistic analyze, cultural peculiarities, pragmatic, specific problems, mistranslation, legal systems, clichés.

Nowadays, the problem of translation of official business documentation has become especially important in the age of close global economic relations.

Translation of legal, economic, diplomatic and official business papers not only requires sufficient knowledge of terms, phrases and expressions, but also depends on the clear comprehension of the structure of a sentence and some specific grammar and syntactical patterns, which are characteristic of this style.

A high level of accuracy is very important when translating legal texts: just one mistranslation can have serious negative repercussions for documents and their holder. Legal texts can be difficult to read, let alone translate. From the differences in legal systems to the lack of equivalence when it comes to certain terms or concepts, there are many challenges when it comes to the translation of legal documents.

Below, we'll take a look at four general challenges faced by legal translators as well as three challenges related to specific documents.

FALSE FRIENDS

Legal terms often share the spelling with common-use words. This can lead to one word having two possible translations in the target language and, therefore, to false friends (words that sound or are spelled similarly in two given languages but actually have different meanings). You can read some example in three languages from the table 1.

Table No. 1

English	Uzbek	Russian
Artist	Artist - aktyor yoki san'atkor, san'at bilan shug'ullanuvchi kishi	Артист - Тот, кто занимается публичным исполнением произведений искусства (об актёре, певце, музыканте и т. п.).
Brilliant – excellent	Brilliant – olmos, qimmatbaho tosh	
Data information	x	Дата - Календарное время какого-н. события, а также помета, указывающая время (год, месяц, число) написания чего-н. (письма, статьи и т. п.).
Magazine – periodical publication containing articles and illustrations, often on a particular subject or aimed at a particular readership.	Magazin – do'kon	Магазин
Bet - risk a sum of money or valued item against someone else's on the basis of the outcome of an unpredictable event such as a race or game.	Bet – yuz [face]inson tana a'zosi	x
Angina- chest pain caused by reduced blood flow to the heart muscles.	Angina – tonzillit	Ангина - тонзиллит
abort	Abort – homilani sun'iy nobud bo'lishi/qilinishi	аборт

DIFFERENT LEGAL SYSTEMS

Every country has its own legal system and documents. They can, of course, have their similarities but it is almost a given that certain terms or concepts that exist in one language will vary or just not exist in the other. This makes an understanding of both the source and target legal systems crucial for any legal translator.

Table No.2

English words	Uzbek equivalents
Vital records offices (if someone translated word by word directly the word vital will be translated like alive- tiriklik then whole word tiriklik qaydlar idoralari]	FXDYO...

Reference	ma'lumotnoma
Extract	Ko'chirma
Certificate	Guvohnoma
Driving license	Haydovchilik guvohnomasi
Public document	Rasmiy tarjima [ommaviy tajima emas]
Public notary	Davlat notariusi [ommaviy yoki rasmiy emas]
Director	Direktor, Lekin principal- maktab direktori.
Governor	Gubernator
Khokim	Hokim-
Khokimiyat	Hokimiyat
Administration	Ma'muriyat / hokimiyat

CHANGING LEGAL SYSTEMS

Laws and legal systems are periodically modified or amended. This means that legal translators must keep up to date with these changes to consistently provide high-quality translations. Subscribing to legal periodicals or keeping update from websites and associations, like *the ATA Law Division (Americans)*, *lex.uz (Uzbek)* or other official web sites and, are great ways to do this.

DOCUMENT-BASED CHALLENGES

a. Contracts. The toughest challenge when it comes to the translation of contracts is avoiding ambiguity. As we've mentioned, legalese can be difficult to understand. Translators need to be aware of the nuances of both languages to deliver a translation that is clear and free of ambiguity.

b. Financial records. Most of us are familiar with the decimal numeral system. However, this system has differences when it comes to English and other languages. Decimals are separated by a decimal point in English, but a comma Russian.

Moreover, some languages have native written numeral systems in addition to the widespread Arabic numerals.

For example: *One million: in Uzbek: 1 000 000, in Russian: 1.000.000,00 and in English: 1,000,000.00*

Legal translators carry a lot of responsibility as a mistake can have critical consequences. This is why they must undergo the appropriate training, be aware of these challenges, and keep abreast of any change

Traditionally distinguish the characteristic features of official documents:

- *traditionality of expression;*
- *coded language system (including abbreviations);*
- *precise and concise wording;*
- *neutral unemotional tone;*
- *impersonal lexical constructions.*

When translating business documents, it is traditionally necessary to follow strict rules and use standard language patterns. In other words, the translator must know the peculiarities of business correspondence and have business etiquette skills.

One of the main distinguishing features of business style is the use of words in their direct dictionary meaning. It should be noted that when translating business documentation, contextual meanings or simultaneous realization of several meanings of a word have no place, as well as emotional meanings.

Phrases and clichés that seem strange when used in spoken English are actively used in business documentation, e.g. 'representative'- "Vakil/vakolatli shaxs" - «представитель», 'adherence'- "muvofiglik/tartib"- «соблюдение», 'suspend' - "to'xtatib turish"- «приостановить», 'evaluation'- "baholash" - «оценка».

When translating official business documents, words of Greek, French, and Latin origin are often used. For example, 'commence' instead of 'begin', 'conclude' instead of 'stop'.

Latin abbreviations such as 'e.g.' ('for example' – "masalan" - «например»), 'et.al.' ('and others'- "va boshqalar" - «и другие»), 'i.e.' ('that is'- "ya'ni" - «то есть»), 'v.v.' ('and vice versa'- "va aksincha" - «и наоборот»). Also use the English abbreviations 'ltd.' ('limited liability'- "mas'uliyati cheklanganli" - «ограниченная ответственность»), 'encl.' ('enclosed'- "ilova qilingan" - «приложено»), 'dols.' ('dollars'- "dollar" - «доллары»), 'Bros.' ('brothers'- "akakalar" - «братья»), 'etc.' ('and so on'- "va shuningdek" - «и так далее»).

The use of the modal verb 'shall' require a specific translation.

For example,

English: *'If the Contractor shall provide the services'*

Uzbek: *"Agar Pudratchi xizmatlarni ko'rsatsa."*

Russian: *"Если Подрядчик будет оказывать услуги"*

Non-personal verb forms (infinitives, participles and -ing forms) are widely used in business English documentation. Verb forms are used in commercial and business correspondence and other forms of English-language communication. The most frequently used verb form is the infinitive. It serves as a complement to verbs,

nouns and adjectives. Accordingly, the infinitive in a sentence can perform a variety of functions: *complement, subject, predicate, circumstance of cause, purpose, etc.*

Contracts are of great interest from the lexico-semantic point of view. The vocabulary of a contract has its own specific features. First of all, it should be noted that the vocabulary is rather stable and is not marked by expressive labeling.

In view of this, we can list the words actually present in each contract.

'Whereas' (*'taking into consideration'*) expresses any thought a person has about how a contract begins. One must be careful in using 'whereas' and not confuse this word with 'where as'.

Another compound word with the adverb 'where' means in the text of the contract 'whereby' implies by 'which' and refers to an existing contract. For example, 'We have concluded the present contract whereby it is agreed as follows.' 'We have concluded the present contract whereby it is agreed as follows'.

'Hereinafter' is a word used in a contract to refer to the parties, to shorten the names of the parties, to make the expression concise. For example, 'Siemens, LLC hereinafter referred to as 'the Company'.

"Siemens, LLC hereinafter referred to as 'the Company'".

Among the grammatical peculiarities in translating official business documents, we can separately point out the active use of modal verbs. In these texts they occur quite often and are used primarily to express politeness:

'would', 'could', 'should', etc.

1. 'The Contractor shall not be liable to the Company and / or any third party for consequential damages from accidents...'

"Pudratchi Kompaniya va/yoki uchunchi shaxslar oldida baxtsiz hodisalardan kelib chiqqan zararlar uchun javobgar bo'lmaydi...".

Подрядчик не несет ответственности перед Компанией и/или любой третьей стороной за косвенные убытки от несчастных случаев...

2. 'Each Party shall take all reasonable steps to preserve any trade secrets or other confidential information provided by the other Party.'

"Har bir Tomon boshqa Tomon taqdim etgan har qanday tijorat sirlarini yoki boshqa maxfiy ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun barcha oqilona choralarni ko'radi."

"Каждая сторона принимает все разумные меры для сохранения любых коммерческих секретов или другой конфиденциальной информации, предоставленной другой стороной".

Contract translation begins with the identification of the type of documentation (financial, contractual, administrative, reporting). The final stage is editing the text and evaluating the terminology used. Special attention should be paid

to non-equivalent vocabulary that does not have regular correspondences in other languages: company names, addresses and surnames. The translator must achieve practical informational equivalence of the translation to the original text.

Abbreviations of the source text should be deciphered and translated according to generally accepted rules. However, abbreviations that cannot be deciphered should be rendered in the original language. It is customary to transcribe (convey the pronunciation by means of written signs) names, surnames, names of economic entities and products of their activities.

Translation of official business documentation should be precise, concise, not wordy, clear, the translation text should lack the syntactic structures of the source language, and it should meet the generally accepted norms of linguistics.

Translation of business documentation is one of the most complex types of translation, as it requires from the translator erudition, awareness of discourse theory, semantics, extensive background knowledge and professional translation competencies. Contracts cannot be translated correctly only if the translator has knowledge of law and economics and the specifics of document flow. There is a strong need for knowledge of business, lexicology and terminology of the source and target languages.

REFERENCES

1. *Izmailov, A.Z. Stylistic transformations in translation from English into Russian / A.Z. Izmailov. Vestnik of Moscow State Regional University. Series "Linguistics": scientific journal. - Moscow: MGOU, 2010. - C. 140-145.*

2. *Ismagilova L.R. Lexical peculiarities of business correspondence translation (on the materials of business letters in English of economic orientation) // VESTNIK*

BSU. Series: Philology. Art History. 2012. - № 21 - C. 57-60.

3. *Lukmanova R.R. Lexical peculiarities of translation of official texts from Russian into English (on the material of documents accompanying an investment project) // Vestnik of Bashkir University. - Ufa: RID EashSU, 2014. - № 4 (T. 19). - C. 1430-1434.*

4. *Lexical features of the text of official documents and Their translation, Nursulton Zamon ugli Shayxislamov*

INTERNET RESOURCES

1. <https://www.lex.uz>
2. <https://www.eE-notarius.uz>
3. <https://www.mfa.uz>
4. <https://www.ata-divisions.org>